

REFORMS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM ARE THE FOUNDATION OF THE FUTURE

Roila Yuldoshvoyevna Xaydarova

Technology teacher at school

№14 of Bostonliq district, Tashkent region

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Abstract. *Due to the dynamics of our social life today, education is also undergoing major reforms. Because reforms in the field of education are the foundation of the future. This article will give a broader opinion about this.*

Keywords: *Education, international assessment programs, innovative development, youth support, foreign experiences, cooperative relations.*

At a time when our country is rapidly developing on the path of innovative development, comprehensive support for the creative ideas and creativity of young people who are the successors of our future, formation of their knowledge, skills and qualifications, and advanced foreign experiences, international standards and improving the evaluation system based on requirements, studying international experiences, comprehensive comparative analysis of the existing system, close cooperation with relevant international and foreign organizations and scientific research institutions is important.

The prosperity and development of the country is determined by the perspective of education and the spiritual maturity of the young generation. It is important for the future owners to have modern knowledge, intellectual potential, knowledge and enlightenment, free thinking, the ability to apply advanced technologies, and apply world-recognized methods and traditions. Reforms in the educational system are aimed at this goal, and the educational technologies used in the highly developed countries of the world, which are highly effective, are focused on the international requirements of evaluation. International assessment programs such as PIRLS, TIMSS, PISA, TALIS are being successfully implemented in the highly developed countries of the world. In our country, which is facing the world with the steps of development, international evaluation criteria are used in the field of education. As it is known, in order to carry out comparative analysis with the countries of the world by evaluating the quality of education based on international standards, on December 8, 2018, the Cabinet of Ministers approved "Measures for the organization of international research in the field of evaluation of the quality of education in the public education system" "on" was adopted. In the decision, a national center for the implementation of international studies on the assessment of the quality of education was established under the State Inspectorate for the control of the quality of education, and it was determined that it would participate in a number of international studies on the determination of the quality of education. In addition, according to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", it should be implemented in the system, which is the main link of the formation of human capital. The tasks and ways of their implementation were defined in detail. In particular, it sets the task of making our country one of the 30 leading countries in the world by 2030 in the rating of PISA (The Program for International Student Assessment) - the international program for evaluating the achievements of students in the

field of education. These changes taking place in public education are directly related to higher education institutions, and are the reason for the increase of cooperation between schools and higher education institutions.

Even if attention is paid directly to the field of higher education, the issuance of a number of laws, decrees and decisions indicates that fundamental changes are taking place in these fields. Here, the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 is based on the provision of a strong integration of science, education and production, based on the needs of the social sphere and economic sectors. It should be noted that it was developed in order to improve the quality, train competitive personnel, effectively organize scientific and innovative activities, and develop international cooperation. The concept defines the strategic goals, priorities, tasks, medium- and long-term stages of the development of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and is the basis for the development of programs and complex measures related to the field, and each higher education institution has defined its "Roadmaps". On this basis, the systematic implementation of scientific research works, training of targeted personnel, creative communication, creation of innovative projects, creation of programs, improvement of the process of integration between theory and practice, quality organization of production and qualification practices of students have been launched. As a result, a number of practical works are being carried out on the cooperation of higher education institutions and schools.

This event will further increase the potential of our national personnel being created in the higher education system and help to assess their creative potential more widely. The most important task of the innovative cooperation agreement between higher education, science and industry in the future is to support, materially and morally stimulate, the learned, talented and skilled students studying at the higher educational institution. This step directly shows the attitude of professors-teachers in the higher education system to international evaluation programs, the need to create its theoretical foundations and scientific justification.

In conclusion, as a result of the reforms carried out in our country in recent years, huge economic growth indicators are being achieved, the demand for skilled personnel and mature specialists in all fields is increasing. This in itself requires increasing the interest of our students in classes and increasing the attention of teachers to all-round education. The fact that the above requirements are very important for the higher education system means that, as in most foreign countries, it is necessary to attract the best practices aimed at improving the quality of education by evaluating and monitoring the development of the fields of education and science.

It should also be said that in the period of changes, the education system requires rapid development based on social processes. Through education, a new generation capable of fulfilling future tasks will be formed in the society. Taking this into account, special attention is being paid to strengthening the material and technical base of general education schools and pre-school educational institutions, to creating the necessary conditions and opportunities for the young generation to receive comprehensive education. Also, the issue of training personnel in the fields of education, the allocation of special quotas for certain fields in the higher education system, and the fact that pedagogical practices are carried out directly in production institutions are proof that the higher education system is undergoing a lot of changes. In particular, the programs that determine the quality, level and level of education in the world - PISA (International Program for

the Assessment of Student Achievement in Education), PIRLS (International Study of Reading and Comprehension of the Text), TIMSS (Mathematics in School and international monitoring researching the quality of exact sciences), there are a number of international programs, which are widely used as a criterion for further improving the quality of education in developed countries, and this use is now taking its place even more its strengthening will increase due to the requirements of the time.

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